

THE HIGH-SPEED CIVIL TRANSPORT: A SUPERSONIC LEAP IN TECHNOLOGY

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SUMMARY: Current production aerospace materials will not satisfy the requirements for a next-generation supersonic transport, currently envisioned as a Mach 2.4 cruise aircraft that carries 300 passengers over 9,260-12,000 km (5000-6500 nm) transoceanic routes. Research sponsored by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration has concluded that titanium alloys and high-temperature polymer-matrix composites are required to meet the elevated temperatures encountered on aerodynamically heated wing and fuselage surfaces during supersonic cruise. This paper presents an overview of the technology challenges facing materials developers and structural designers for the High-Speed Civil Transport (HSCT). Significant progress has been achieved in the development of lightweight, durable, damage-tolerant wing and fuselage structural concepts using advanced polymeric composites and hybrid laminate systems. Highlights of design, analysis, fabrication and test of innovative sandwich and skin-stiffened structural concepts are presented.

KEYWORDS: high-speed civil transport, HSCT, high-speed research program, HSR, SST, Concorde, sandwich, honeycomb

INTRODUCTION

For over two decades, air travelers have waited for aerospace manufacturers to launch a successor to the world's only surviving supersonic transport, the Mach 2.0 Concorde. The Anglo-French venture was hailed as a technical marvel when it entered service in 1976, but it never reached economic expectations [1]. The Russian TU-144 entered passenger service shortly after the Concorde but technical problems and two crashes led to a very brief operational career [2]. The United States' foray into the supersonic transport (SST) niche was marked with great enthusiasm during the 1960's but was eventually terminated by Congress in 1971 due to political and environmental opposition [3].

During the SST heyday, the U.S. aerospace industry also developed long-range supersonic military aircraft (B-58, XB-70, and SR-71) and high-capacity, long range subsonic airplanes (747, DC-10, and L-1011). However, the issues of airline economics, passenger safety, airframe life, airplane maintenance, airport noise, and environmental impact were significantly different for SST designs. Fortunately, Advanced Supersonic Transport research continued during the 1970's and 1980's (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Timeline of Supersonic Transport Development

Since the demise of the U. S. SST program, there has been significant technology progress that could lead to a Concorde successor that is both economically viable and environmentally acceptable. Improvements in propulsion, aerodynamics, electronic flight deck systems, and advanced materials and structures have been applied to a next-generation supersonic transport design that could see service as early as the year 2010. This High-Speed Civil Transport (HSCT) (Fig. 2) is currently under research by the United States government and industry.

Fig. 2: The proposed Mach 2.4 High-Speed Civil Transport (HSCT) will supersede the Concorde as the next-generation supersonic passenger aircraft

HIGH-SPEED CIVIL TRANSPORT DEVELOPMENT

In 1986, President Reagan announced the X-30 National Aero-Space Plane program (Fig. 3). This program was to develop two spaceplane prototypes that would demonstrate the technology required for reusable “single-stage-to-orbit,” aircraft [4]. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration, keenly aware of the benefits of hypersonic military technology applied to the development of a new commercial SST, issued contracts to Boeing and Douglas Aircraft in late 1986 to study a range of Mach numbers. Both companies selected vehicle configurations that cruised between Mach 2.0 and 2.4. These new designs became known as the HSCT.

Fig. 3: X-30 National Aero-Space Plane Ushered In Renewed Aeronautics Research

World passenger traffic growth forecasts showed a considerable advantage for faster-than-sound travel between international city pairs for both passengers and the airline industry, especially for the growing Pacific Rim nations of Asia (Fig. 4). As much as 50% of the year 2015 and year 2025 total passenger markets could be suitable for a future HSCT. The success of this venture depended on an airplane that could meet the stringent airport noise restrictions along with low operating costs for the airlines and quick turnaround times at airport destinations. If an airplane could be built to fly at Mach 2.4 (2,550 kph or 1,584 mph), with a range of 9,260-12,000 km (5,000-6,500 nm), and carry 250-300 passengers, the aerospace industry would be willing to raise the multi-billion dollar investment to develop, launch, and certify the HSCT.

By 1990, NASA had formed a High-Speed Research Phase I Program (HSR I) to concentrate the efforts within the aerospace industry, government agencies, university laboratories, and material suppliers. Initially, the focus keyed in on the shortcomings of the U. S. SST, namely, ozone depletion, engine noise, and sonic boom damage.

Fig. 4: HSCT Flight Time Reductions for International Routes

NASA HIGH-SPEED RESEARCH PHASE II PROGRAM

Favorable progress during Phase I of the NASA High-Speed Research Program was made in meeting the challenge of protecting the environment, thus, additional research was begun to develop the key technologies for creating a profitable airplane. These include advanced aerodynamics, efficient engines, lightweight materials and structures, and an electronic flight deck. In 1994, NASA Langley Research Center (NASA-LaRC) embarked on a US\$1.7 billion, seven-year program designated High-Speed Research Phase II (HSR II). NASA-LaRC, Boeing and McDonnell Douglas are leading the airframe technology development program, while NASA Lewis Research Center, General Electric Aircraft Engines, and Pratt & Whitney are teamed together on engine technology development. In addition, HSR II combines the talents of other aerospace manufacturers, universities, material suppliers, and small businesses throughout the country.

Early vehicle design studies conducted by Boeing and McDonnell Douglas determined tentative goals for an HSCT concept (Fig. 5): Mach 2.4 cruise speed; 300 passengers; 340,200 kg (750,000 lb.) maximum takeoff weight, and a 9,260 km (5,000 nm) range. In 1995 a common Technology Concept Aircraft baseline was agreed upon to assess the necessary technology required to launch an HSCT program. Primary emphasis was given to the

aerodynamic shaping of the wing and fuselage in order to reduce drag during supersonic cruise and to reduce noise levels during takeoff and landing.

Fig. 5: HSCT Materials & Structures Selection

AIRFRAME MATERIALS & STRUCTURES TECHNOLOGY

Key to the economic success of the HSCT are lightweight materials that can withstand the elevated surface temperatures encountered at cruising speeds three times that of current subsonic jets. Moreover, these structural concepts must be durable enough to last for a lifetime of over 20,000 flights that includes 60,000 hours at cruise temperatures. The temperatures due to aerodynamic friction are in excess of that encountered by normal commercial jetliners (Fig. 6). At the nose tip, wing leading edges, and tail leading edges, the temperatures are expected to reach 177°C (350°F). This long-term thermal environment is the major driver for the airframe structure in terms of safety, weight, durability, cost, and risk.

Fig. 6: Skin Temperatures During Mach 2.4 Cruise

Four major technology areas are being pursued by dedicated teams of U.S. government and industry participants. These include materials development, wing structures, fuselage structures, and airframe integration.

Materials Development

Metallic Materials

Titanium materials are being developed with 15-20 percent improvement in specific properties over conventional aerospace materials at the HSCT operating environments for up to 60,000 hours. Variations of existing titanium alloys and novel fabrication processes are under development to improve the strength, toughness, stiffness, and production cost of formed structure. The primary emphasis of the metals development is on sandwich skin panels for highly loaded wing applications (Fig. 7). Fabrication processes are being refined at McDonnell Douglas and Boeing to produce bonded titanium honeycomb and superplastically-formed, diffusion bonded titanium structure.

Fig. 7: Superplastically-Formed, Diffusion Bonded Titanium Sandwich Structures Use Advanced Titanium Alloys To Increase the Strength and Stiffness

Composites, Adhesives & Sealants

Long life polymer-matrix composites (PMC), adhesives, sealants, and associated material forms are also under development along with application and fabrication processes to meet the operating environment of the HSCT. Elevated temperature PMCs and structural adhesives with strength superior to existing materials are required for large acreage wing and fuselage skin panels. These bonded structures include PMC honeycomb sandwich and PMC skin-stiffened constructions (Fig. 8). Boeing, Northrop Grumman Corporation and McDonnell Douglas are producing autoclave-cured structure using polyimide resin system tape. In-situ consolidation trials are underway to produce laminates without the need for autoclave curing.

Boeing has produced a unique hybrid laminate system using interleaved titanium foil sheets between PMC plies. The titanium increases the damage tolerance of the laminate, while the PMC plies increase the fatigue life beyond the titanium failure point. Critical to the success of this laminate design is a successful surface preparation that results in a high-strength adhesive bond. Both wing and fuselage skin panels could benefit from this laminate construction.

Finally, durable high temperature fuel tank sealants are being investigated, since no sealants are currently available that can survive one airframe lifetime under HSCT thermal conditions.

Fig. 8: Lightweight Structural Composites Will Meet HSCT Life and Temperature Requirements

Materials Durability

Critical for commercial transports, the selected materials must be able to withstand two lifetimes at temperatures much higher than those encountered during subsonic flight. A materials database will be generated that characterizes the short-term and long-term characteristics of metallic and composite materials subjected to long exposures to both elevated temperature (Fig. 9) and structural loads. PMCs are most vulnerable to long term degradation over time, and thermomechanical aging is being conducted at NASA-LaRC and California State University – Long Beach. Bolt bearing studies at Lockheed Martin Aeronautical Systems and bearing creep tests at Georgia Institute of Technology are investigating thermal effects on thick PMC laminates.

Fig. 9: Long-Term Thermomechanical Aging of HSCT Materials

Wing Structures

Metallic and composite structural concepts that meet the thermal and mechanical loads of the HSCT will be designed, fabricated, and tested. A progressive, building-block approach will be used to design and develop representative subcomponents for the main wing box, forward

strake, and outboard wing. The final validation will be led by McDonnell Douglas at the end of HSR II with a full-scale test of the HSCT main wing box (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: Full-Scale HSCT Main Wing Box Component Test Article

Fuselage Structures

Candidate fuselage design concepts that meet the passenger safety requirements of the HSCT are also being developed. Flying at 18,300 meters (60,000 feet), catastrophic failure of an HSCT fuselage skin panel is of utmost concern. Lightweight, damage resistant structures are under development in a building-block approach for the forward, mid, and aft fuselage sections. A full-scale fuselage barrel test (Fig. 11) led by Boeing is also planned for the end of HSR II and will be tested at the NASA Langley Research Center Combined Loads Test System (COLTS) facility.

Fig. 11: Full-Scale HSCT Aft Fuselage Component Test Article Airframe Integration

Structural Dynamics

Under flight loads, the wing and fuselage experiences flutter that can affect both the HSCT performance and safety. This was one of the most challenging engineering problems associated with the original U.S. SST design. To mitigate these risks, computational methods

and wind tunnel models (Fig. 12) are being used to predict the onset of flutter and adverse aeroelastic effects without the need for additional vehicle weight.

Fig. 12: HSCT Flutter Analysis Correlated to Wind Tunnel Tests

Structural Acoustics

HSCT performance and safety will be improved by eliminating sonic fatigue of structural parts due to turbulent boundary layer airflow and engine jet exhaust noise levels. Passenger comfort will be enhanced by minimizing transmission of this noise into the fuselage cabin by either active or passive suppression techniques. Using active control techniques, significant reductions in broadband noise were achieved over a large cabin volume (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13: Active Noise Suppression Techniques Will Minimize Cabin Noise Levels

Design/Integration Trade Studies

Airframe assessments are continually performed to reduce the overall weight of the HSCT and to integrate the various materials and structures technologies into a viable airplane design. Structural optimization uses large finite element models that represent the airframe structure to minimize the weight of each structural member.

CONCLUSION

As the United States enters the twenty-first century, the world has truly become a unified industry. International commerce and trade are now the most important factors of a balanced political and economical global culture. Although NASA is sponsoring much of the base research to develop HSCT technologies, no one company or country will be able to design and build such an airplane. Therefore, Boeing and McDonnell Douglas have joined a Supersonic Commercial Transport International Study Group to study the market needs and economics of a future HSCT. Other participants include Aerospatiale (France), Alenia (Italy), British Aerospace, Daimler Benz Aerospace (Germany), Japan Aircraft Industries, and Tupolev (Russia).

With the High-Speed Research investment by the U. S. Government through NASA aeronautics research, the American aerospace industry will be poised to help launch a fleet of HSCTs that will encourage a new future for global aviation.

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